

ELIXIR Tools Platform

2024-26

Work Plan

Abstract

The Tools Platform provides services that enable findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of computational tools: including research software, workflows, remote digital services, and trained machine-learning (ML) models.

During the 2024-26 programme, the ELIXIR Tools Platform aims to:

- Allow researchers (end-users) to find well-described and fit-for-purpose research software, providing alternatives when available, that can be used in heterogeneous computational setups from a laptop to a cloud installation to an HPC centre;
- Serve as reference point for individual research software engineers on how to develop better, more sustainable, and recognizable software by providing best practices and services supporting such an endeavour;
- Provide scientific communities with a reference place for tackling common challenges in their own best practices for software development.

The Platform consists of five Work Packages (WPs):

WP1: Platform management and coordination

WP2: The ELIXIR Research Software Ecosystem

WP3: Software management, stewardship and standards

WP4: Defining a roadmap towards reproducible and distributed analysis using benchmarking

WP5: Democratised access to reusable complex workflows

The Tools Platform services are optimised for the needs of life science researchers, but are also applicable in interdisciplinary applications and scientific communities, including through the European Open Science Cloud. The overall goal of the Tools Platform is to sustain the required services and expand them to fulfil the needs of the ELIXIR Programme 2024-2028.

This document shows the work plan version as approved by the ELIXIR Board in November 2023.

About this document

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1. Objectives and relation to the Scientific Programme

The ELIXIR Tools Platform is strategically aligned with the focal points of the Scientific Programme, serving key priorities in Technology, Node development, and People capacity. Under the Technology Priority, the platform embarks on an ambitious objective to upscale federated data management and analytics in life sciences. By further developing the Research Software Ecosystem, the platform aims to achieve seamless curation and federated access to research software metadata. This, in turn, ensures that analytics can be universally reproduced across different computational environments. Another critical objective is to evolve the biotoolsSchema and EDAM standards, which enhances the federated delivery of services, allowing for more robust, interoperable systems across research communities. Capitalising on the success of the previous programme, the Tools Platform aims to continue evolving the Software Management Plans by improving the Software Management Wizard into more stable releases, reviewing and using important new technological features such as introducing machine actionability and staying relevant to modern advancements in the field.

In terms of the Node Priority, the ELIXIR Tools Platform aims to equip ELIXIR Nodes for sustainable, long-term operations. The Work Packages have a multifaceted approach that aligns with national research and open science policies, focusing on delivering up-to-date guidelines and standards. Additionally, the platform acts as a lynchpin for innovation by serving as a reference point for research software engineers. The focus on quality, findability, and standardisation of software and services ensures that the platform not only has a significant impact but is also equipped for long-term sustainability. For example, services that connect to the Research Software Ecosystem are "safeguarded" by having their data and metadata stored and archived irrespective of their current funding status, thus increasing their sustainability plans in case of funding brevity that leads to services stopping to operate.

As for People Priority, the platform is designed to enhance the capacities of both end-users and technical staff. The platform's commitment to making research tools more findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable enables researchers to perform groundbreaking work. Concurrently, it offers avenues for software and workflow developers to contribute to the ecosystem. By focusing on delivering up-to-date standards and best practices, it aids in the professional development of both technical and scientific staff.

Overall, the ELIXIR Tools Platform is well-positioned to meet the objectives of the Scientific Programme, creating a sustainable, adaptable, and user-centric ecosystem geared to meet the scientific challenges of the future.

2. Partnership

Contributors to the work programme are listed in **Table 1. Table 1.** Overview of involved institutions. Leads highlighted in **bold**.

Node	Institution	Abbreviation
DE	University of Freiburg (Lead)	ES-Freiburg
ES	Barcelona Supercomputer Centre (Lead)	ES-BSC
FR	Institut Pasteur (Lead)	FR-IPasteur
BE	VIB	BE-VIB
CH	SIB	CH-SIB
CZ	MUNI	CZ-MUNI
DE	Julich	DE-FZJU
DK	University of Southern Denmark	DK-DSU
DK	Copenhagen	DK-UNICOP
EE	University of Tartu	EE-UTARTU
ELIXIR	ELIXIR Hub	ELIXIR-HUB
EMBL	European Bioinformatics Institute	EMBL-EBI
EMBL	Heidelberg	EMBL-HD
FR	Nantes	FR-CNRS
FR	IRISA	FR-IRISA
FR	UniLorraine	FR-UNILorraine
GR	CERTH	GR-INAB/CERTH
IT	Bologna	IT-UNIBO
IT	Sapienza	IT-UNIROMA ₁
NL	Leiden University Medical Center	NL-Leiden
NO	University of Bergen	NO-UiB
SE	University of Uppsala	SE-UU
UK	Manchester	UK-UNIMAN
UK	Earlham	UK-Earlham

International Partners		
AU	University of Melbourne	AU-Melbourne
DE	ZBMed	DE-ZBMed
US	CALMI	US-CALMI

3. Work Package descriptions

Work Package 1 - Platform Management and Coordination

WP 1	Lead Partner: DE-Freiburg, ES-BSC, FR-IPasteur	
	Start month-End month: Mo1-M36	
WP Partnership		
DE-Freiburg - Björn Grüning (Lead)		
ES-BSC - Salvador Capella (Lead)		
FR-IPasteur - Hervé Ménager (Lead)		
ELIXIR-HUB - Jonathan Tedds (Coordinator), Technical Officer		
Objectives		
<p>The purpose of this work package is to provide the overall project management and coordination of the activities of ELIXIR Tools platform. This work package ensures that platform work progresses as planned.</p> <p>The work package will also ensure that the platform work plan is aligned with ELIXIR’s strategic vision, and the overall development of European research infrastructures, data spaces and regulation. The work package facilitates active dialog with life-science research communities in order to understand the real needs of researchers. This is done especially by collaborating with ELIXIR Communities that represent researchers’ use cases.</p> <p>Besides technology development, delivering impact on research requires that the technology can be sustained and provided for researchers. This work package seeks ways how the developed technology can be sustained as part of operational services. This can be done both by integrating technology into existing services and by establishing new services when applicable.</p> <p>The landscape of European research infrastructures, data spaces and related initiatives, such as EOSC, EuroHPC and GAIA-X, are evolving and the work package is actively participating in this development. Establishing services in cross-infrastructure fashion and providing them in wider collaboration is seen as a favourable option. Especially partnering with other research infrastructures and providing services as part of EOSC service offering supports the objective of long term service sustainability. Also, the work package ensures that the platform activities are well connected and communicated to the research community.</p> <p>The work package will also bridge the platform activities to GA4GH and participate in the steering of GA4GH by utilising the ELIXIR and GA4GH strategic partnership.</p>		
Description of Work		
Activity 1: Platform Management and Coordination		
<i>Leads: DE-Freiburg (Björn Grüning), ES-BSC (Salvador Capella), FR-IPasteur (Hervé Ménager)</i>		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Set up and facilitate regular platform wide meetings, both online and face-to-face ● Provide proper communication channels for the work ● Monitor and report the progress 		
Activity 2: Sustainability and Dissemination		
<i>Leads: DE-Freiburg (Björn Grüning), ES-BSC (Salvador Capella), FR-IPasteur (Hervé Ménager)</i>		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ensure sufficient sustainability planning for platform development activities 		

- Ensure bi-directional communication about the platform activities towards research communities, especially through ELIXIR Communities, ELIXIR Training Platform and utilising existing communications channels such as ELIXIR webinars
- Knowledge sharing with other ELIXIR platforms and participation in joint-platform activities
- Represent platform in EOSC, EuroHPC and the ELIXIR::GA4GH strategic partnership
- Dissemination for Tools Platform

Deliverable	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
D1.1	Annual Report 2023	FR-IPasteur	Mo6
D1.2	Annual Report 2024	DE-Freiburg	M18
D1.3	Annual Report 2025	ES-BSC	M30
D1.4	Alignment to prospective ELIXIR Cross Platform dissemination articles	FR-IPasteur	M30
D1.5	Preparation, writing and delivery of 2027-2028 Platform Plan	ES-BSC	M30
D1.6	End Report	DE-Freiburg	M36
Milestone	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
M1.1	Platform F2F Event - Year 1	ES-BSC	M12
M1.2	Platform F2F Event - Year 2	DE-Freiburg	M24
M1.3	Platform F2F Event - Year 3	FR-IPasteur	M36

Work Package 2 - The ELIXIR Research Software Ecosystem

WP 2	Lead Partner: FR-IPasteur, NL-Leiden, DK-DSU, CZ-MUNI	
	Start month-End month: Mo1-M36	
WP Partnership		
FR-IPasteur - Hervé Ménager		
NL-Leiden - Magnus Palmblad		
DK-DSU - Veit Schwämmle		
CZ-MUNI - Radka Svobodová, Adrián Rošinec, Tomáš Raček		
DE-Freiburg - Björn Grüning		
GR-INAB/CERTH - Fotis Psomopoulos		
NO-UiB - Matúš Kalaš		
FR-CNRS- Alban Gaignard		
ES-BSC - Salvador Capella, Eva Martin del Pico		
EE-UTARTU - Hedi Peterson		
IT-UNIBO - Emidio Capriotti		
External		
AU-Melbourne - Johan Gustafsson		
Objectives		
<p>The ELIXIR Research Software Ecosystem (RSEc) collates and publishes informative descriptions of more than 30,000 software tools and services. Most of these records are provided and curated using the bio.tools registry, which is synchronised with the backend of the Ecosystem.</p> <p>WP2 will further develop the RSEc as a way to enable federated access and curation of reference metadata of any research software. This activity will leverage the technical and scientific expertise of the various communities and services within and beyond ELIXIR (e.g. Galaxy and WorkflowHub, both WP5).</p> <p>This development will target direct contribution mechanisms for software and workflow developers, so that metadata provided during the software publication and release process can be seamlessly consumed, and synchronised with the Ecosystem. Additional mechanisms will enable full coverage of research software metadata directly from the source-code repositories, as well as contributing these from the Ecosystem, through bidirectional synchronisation. These mechanisms will use and drive the evolution of standards such as biotoolsSchema and EDAM (WP3).</p>		
Description of Work		
<p>Activity 1: Designing a software metadata editor for the ecosystem <i>Leads: CZ-MUNI (Adrián Rošinec), FR-IPasteur (Hervé Ménager)</i></p>		

The registration and edition of software metadata in different parts of the ecosystem (e.g. bio.tools) relies on separate user interface components. One of the major components is the entry edition component of bio.tools. The quality and features of this component has a major impact on the adoption of bio.tools, and by extension, the research software ecosystem. We will leverage the evolutions of the ecosystem to facilitate the edition of software metadata, by designing a new software metadata editor.

Activity 2: Defining the next generation of the bio.tools search UI and backend

Leads: DK-DSU (Veit Schwämmle), NL-Leiden (Magnus Palmblad)

The search function in the bio.tools registry is its most important functionality, as it usually represents the first access point to bio.tools, and even the ecosystem itself. As such, it is an essential part for the findability of the referenced software. The current solution, although highly functional, has also demonstrated some limitations. For instance, the current search functionality does not exploit the reasoning capabilities provided by EDAM (e.g. taking into account the class hierarchy of EDAM concepts in the search). In addition, the additional metadata provided by other resources through the ecosystem are not incorporated in the current interface. Our goal is to design the next version of the search interface of bio.tools. There are therefore two components to include, the backend capabilities of the search engine itself, and the user interface which has to provide an access to these capabilities.

Activity 3: Outreach

Leads: NL-Leiden (Magnus Palmblad), EE-UTARTU (Hedi Peterson)

Actively engaging with publishers and funders at the national and international level. Our outreach efforts will be focused on building partnerships with organisations such as EOSC and RDA, as well as academic publishers and literature resources. We will develop, in collaboration with these organisations as well as ELIXIR communities, guidelines that promote good practices in publishing software metadata. The provided guidelines, documentation and templates will help research software developers in providing the required metadata that should accompany published research, to ensure that all relevant information is captured and made available to the scientific community.

Activity 4: Expanding the Ecosystem

Leads: FR-CNRS (Alban Gaignard), NO-UiB (Matúš Kaláš)

We recognize the importance of aligning our efforts with other initiatives in the scientific community, such as CodeMeta. To further support the advancement of science and facilitate collaboration, we are expanding our efforts beyond traditional scientific software to include machine learning models. Inclusion of reusable ML models and connecting to current efforts will improve the relevance, “market” value, and synergies of the Research Software Ecosystem. Given the current momentum and growing interest in the field of machine learning, we will explore the options for enabling the Ecosystem users to find information about reusable ML models - as reusable tools - from ML model registries and platforms (e.g. Hugging Face or Biolmage.io).

Deliverable	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
D2.1	Full design plans to implement or adapt an existing solution that provides the required functionalities. These plans would include a UI static prototype that specifies the features of the finished product	CZ-MUNI	M36
D2.2	Mockup and design plan to implement a new version of the bio.tools search user interface	DK-DSU	M36
D2.3	Recommendations for software developers/authors, reviewers and editors for dissemination of research software metadata	NL-Leiden	M24
D2.4	Outreach to external stakeholders and plan for continuous engagement	NL-Leiden	M36

D2.5	Alignment and consolidation of Bioschemas (Tool, Workflow), biotoolsSchema, and CodeMeta	FR-CNRS	M26
D2.6	Prototype(s) to connect with prioritised ML registries relevant for the Research Software Ecosystem users	NO-UiB	M36
Milestone	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
M2.1	Review of software metadata edition systems and components that are available, for life sciences research and beyond	CZ-MUNI	M24
M2.2	Gap review of bio.tools UI	DK-DSU	M24

Work Package 3 - Software management, stewardship and standards

WP 3	Lead Partner: NO-UiB, ES-BSC	
	Start month- End month: M01-M36	
WP Partnership		
NO-UiB - Matúš Kalaš		
ES-BSC - Eva Martin del Pico		
DK-DSU - Veit Schwämmle		
DK-UNICOP - Piotr Chmura		
NL-Leiden - Magnus Palmblad		
GR-INAB/CERTH - Fotis Psomopoulos		
FR-CNRS - Alban Gaignard		
FR-IPasteur - Hervé Ménager		
IT-UNIBO - Emidio Capriotti		
SE-UU - Dimitris Bampalakis		
IT-UNIROMA1 - Allegra Via		
EE-UTARTU - Hedi Peterson		
CZ-MUNI - Helge Hecht		
BE-VIB - Rafael Andrade Buono		
CH-SIB - Ana Claudia Sima		
DE-Freiburg - Sebastian Schaaf		
External		
AU-Melbourne - Johan Gustafsson		
DE-ZBMed - Leyla Castro		
US-CALMI - Bhavesh Patel		
<p>Objectives</p> <p>This Work Package will be responsible for guidelines, standards, and knowledge sharing dedicated to making research software FAIR. It will promote principles of software management and best practices, deliver up-to-date standards for describing software and other research objects, and disseminate these in the form of software stewardship. The required standards include EDAM, data models and information standards for recording information ("metadata") about research software, and templates for creating software management plans (SMPs).</p>		

EDAM is widely used by most ELIXIR Platforms and Communities, as one of the common knowledge management standards. It serves findability, provenance, and interoperability. WP3 will contribute to keeping EDAM up to date, and coordinate EDAM extensions by ELIXIR Communities, Nodes, and affiliated projects, covering their needs.

SMPs play the same role as DMPs, but for software. The ELIXIR SMP is low-barrier, tailored for life scientists, and fully aligned with the FAIR Research Software principles. A software management portal will be designed linking knowledge, training materials, and services through a single entry point. It will provide quality metrics including FAIRness assessment (connected to WP4 and the Training Platform) and the utility of machine-actionable SMPs will be investigated.

WP3 will also work together with other WPs, Platforms, and global initiatives, on delivering data models and information standards for describing software-based resources, and enhancing citations. This WP will engage with international organisations dealing with research software, such as EOSC, RDA, NIH, and Australian BioCommons.

We will also work towards expanding the software best practices to further domains (such as AI/ML).

Description of work

Software Best Practices

Software best practices cover guidelines, standards, and software sharing aligned to the FAIR for software principles (and extensions that might arise later, e.g., ML). WP3.1 will promote: Best Practices in Research Software, machine actionability, quality indicators, training and capacity building, metadata delivery. Moreover, it will align and build on the efforts around Research Software Quality indicators and metrics (such as EVERSE, ELIXIR-STEERS, etc.).

Activity 1: Best Practices in Research Software

Leads: ES-BSC (Eva Martin del Pico), GR-INAB/CERTH (Fotis Psomopoulos)

Building on the success of the Software Best Practices group, we will expand the effort to capture best practices across relevant efforts, such as Machine Learning (aligning also to the RDA FAIR4ML group) and web applications. The first step will be to perform a community review of the specific domain, and will consequently reprise the approach taken for the software best practices, i.e. defining the minimal set/low barrier actions (such as the 4OSS), review the connection the FAIR principles (similar to FAIR4RS), ultimately leading to a structure format to capture relevant information (such as the SMP).

Activity 2. Machine actionability in Software

Leads: ES-BSC (Eva Martin del Pico), GR-INAB/CERTH (Fotis Psomopoulos)

Machine actionability makes interoperability easier for machines while also enabling metadata-based links across tools within the Tools Ecosystem, as well as across relevant efforts in other domains. In the case of Software Management Plans it brings a common ground making it easier for different stakeholders to review and assess the information captured through the SMPs. We will refine / tune the current metadata schemas that were produced from the joint RDA/EOSC-Future / ZBMed / ELIXIR project on machine-actionable SMP, while also establishing better connections to the bioschemas community. Moreover, and based on this effort, we will integrate the metadata schema into the Software Management Wizard, ultimately transforming questionnaire-based information captured in the wizard into maSMPs (machine-actionable)SMPs. Finally, we will review engagement strategies to connect and align to other relevant national (e.g. NFDI4DataScience, eScience Center Netherlands) and international (e.g. RDA, SWH) initiatives.

Activity 3. Quality indicators for Software

Leads: ES-BSC (Eva Martin del Pico), GR-INAB/CERTH (Fotis Psomopoulos)

Using the existing efforts around research software quality (such as EOSC, NFDI, etc), this task will aim to map and align the various indicators to the existing and/or planned services (e.g. OpenEBench), tools (e.g.

Software Observatory, FAIR-Checker) and frameworks (e.g. SMPs, Bioschemas) that exist within the Tools Platform ecosystem.

Activity 4. Training and capacity building for Software

Leads: ES-BSC (Eva Martin del Pico), GR-INAB/CERTH (Fotis Psomopoulos)

Continue to expand the TeSS collection of courses and materials around Best Practices (currently including the 4OSS and the new SMP) with existing relevant resources from within and beyond ELIXIR (such as Carpentries, GOBLET, GTN, etc), and in a co-production model with the Peoples' Tier CoS. Additionally, new training material will be created to capture the research software quality aspects, connecting the respective Tools Platform and the Training Platform activities. Moreover, and in close collaboration with the Learning Pathways Focus Group, we will co-develop and design dedicated learning pathways around research software.

Activity 5: Application of EDAM ontology to ELIXIR Communities and diverse ELIXIR Services

Leads: Matúš Kalaš (NO), Hervé Ménager (FR)

Technical and community capacity building for the EDAM ontology is required for keeping EDAM up to date with the evolution and challenges of biosciences and global issues. Our focus is on enabling ELIXIR Communities to expand the ontology and ensuring that it encapsulates their needs, in order to facilitate seamless findability and provenance of new methods, and enable scientists to easily find and utilise existing resources. Through our efforts, we aim to support the development of robust and user-friendly platforms that empower researchers to explore and leverage the wealth of resources and knowledge available in the scientific community, now also extending beyond life sciences. This would also entail embedding EDAM in as many practical step-by-step guides and training workshops as possible, and aiming for interoperability with other main ontologies & linked open data. We will aim at further refining EDAM for improved performance of AI applications such as the text mining to annotate and add to bio.tools or to enrich scientific articles, assisted workflow generation and provenance, and others.

Direction:

- To convince communities to adopt EDAM
- Investigate linkages to ML activities on annotating datasets
 - ML models for image analysis is connected but missing a more streamlined process of implementation
 - Investigate the description of the datasets that are used to train ML and if they could be captured by EDAM

Stretch goals:

- Community guidelines for the adoption and extension of EDAM to fit their domain-specific needs.
 - Virtual Workshops
- Improvement of the EDAM-browser system to enable the exploration of all annotated resources (e.g. software, training materials, data resources, publications).
 - Proteomics Standards Initiative – potentially synergy
- Connection with other Focus Groups

Deliverable	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
D3.1	A first version of the ELIXIR maSMP	ES-BSC	M36
D3.2	A mapping of the selected software quality indicators against the indicators produced or captured by OpenEBench, ELIXIR maSMP, Software Observatory and other services of the ELIXIR Research Software Ecosystem	ES-BSC	M36
D3.3	A new version of EDAM, incorporating updates for ELIXIR Communities, Services, and AI applications	NO-UiB	M36

Milestone	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
M3.1	Selection of the particular community/domain for the best practices	ES-BSC	Mo6
M3.2	A set of simple best practices, produced for the selected domain	ES-BSC	M36
M3.3	A list of the existing efforts that are capturing/describing research software quality	ES-BSC	M18
M3.4	A learning pathway focused on software best practices	ES-BSC	M36
M3.5	Improved mappings to the major linked open data resources, incl. the most relevant ontologies	NO-UiB	M11
M3.6	Refined, updated EDAM concepts supporting the needs of engaged ELIXIR Communities and Services	NO-UiB	M23

Work Package 4 - Defining a roadmap towards reproducible and distributed analysis using benchmarking

WP 4	Lead Partner: IT-UNIBO, FR-IRISA
	Start month-End month: M01-M36
WP Partnership	
FR-IRISA - Mateo Boudet	
IT-UNIBO - Pier Luigi Martelli	
GR-INAB/CERTH - Fotis Psomopoulos	
FR-CNRS - Alban Gaignard	
DE-Freiburg - Björn Grüning	
IT-UNIBO - Emidio Capriotti, Castrense Savojardo	
<p>Objectives</p> <p>In life sciences, an intensive data-driven discipline, research software is used in a distributed - including more advanced federated solutions - manner across heterogeneous computational infrastructures. Distributed use includes scenarios ranging from individual software used in a unique place, to tools being used across different installations, to more sophisticated approaches, such as federated learning. Despite the increase in complexity, these approaches share many underlying considerations with this WP focusing on three particular aspects:</p> <p>First, this WP will promote and support the organisation of scientific benchmarking efforts driven by research communities. Research communities are essential as they act as a proxy to identify domain-specific challenges, representative datasets associated with them and approaches to evaluate research software tackling those challenges. Moreover, well-established communities can provide reference implementations within their domain of expertise and ensure that the software evolves as the domain does.</p> <p>Third, this WP will put efforts into packaging and containerisation of individual research software (single components/workflows), to enable its distribution and deployment across heterogeneous computational systems, following existing best practices and using existing frameworks. This WP should also strongly contribute towards the reproducibility and replicability of research outcomes, for reliability and provenance, and serve as a reference point to interact with other Platforms, e.g. ELIXIR Compute.</p>	
<p>Description of Work</p> <p>Activity 1: Defining standards for benchmarking datasets across emerging communities <i>leads: IT-UNIBO (Pier Luigi Martelli), FR-IRISA (Alban Gaignard)</i></p> <p>For emerging communities, while benchmarking is important for ensuring that the performance of different computational efforts and approaches can be compared and evaluated objectively, we have observed that only a few people are currently working on this, in particular towards defining datasets (synthetic or otherwise) that can be used to assess this. To address this issue, we plan to leverage the wide range of diverse ELIXIR communities to identify individuals who are passionate about benchmarking and have them champion these efforts. By establishing a community of practice focused on benchmarking, we aim to support the development of rigorous standards and practices that can be adopted widely across the</p>	

scientific community.

Plan of work:

- Defining datasets that can be used for benchmarking within OpenEBench

Activity 2: Facilitating benchmarking through containerisation

Leads: FR-IRISA (Mateo Boudet), DE-Freiburg (Björn Grüning)

Easy and reproducible deployments are a necessity for modern data science. It gets even more important when distributed analysis are becoming more important and broadly used by researchers. Containers, and especially the Bioconda based BioContainers have proven to be a reliable source to tackle the deployment issues across clouds, HPCs and local deployments. BioContainers are used by Nextflow, Snakemake and Galaxy and are therefore a pillar of state-of-the art workflows. In this WP we will continue our Container efforts, adapt to new architectures (ARM, RISC-5) and support the workflow community to create containers as they are needed. This includes a special set of containers dedicated for the benchmarking use-cases selected by the involved communities (WP4.1).

Plan of work:

- Enhance the Biocontainers infrastructure to build ARM compatible packages and containers
- Mirror and sustain more container mirrors around the world

Deliverable	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
D4.1	FAIRification of the benchmarking datasets from the communities selected in M3.1, including an investigation into the respective metadata schemas that can be employed (Bioschemas, etc)	IT-UNIBO	M26
D4.2	Facilitate connection of the benchmarking datasets within the OpenEBench ecosystem	IT-UNIBO	M36
D4.3	First ARM-compatible Biocontainers deployed	FR-IRISA	M24
Milestone	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
M4.1	Selection of two communities from within the ELIXIR Priorities and Ambitions	IT-UNIBO	Mo6

Work Package 5 - Democratised access to reusable complex workflows

WP 4	Lead Partner: UK-UNIMAN, BE-VIB	
	Start month-End month: M01-M36	
WP Partnership		
UK-UNIMAN - Stian Soiland-Reyes		
BE-VIB - Rafael Andrade Buono		
UK-Earlham - Nicola Soranzo		
DE-Freiburg - Björn Grüning		
NO-UNIBO - Matúš Kalaš		
UK-UNIMAN - Stuart Owen, Finn Bacall, Carole Goble		
FR-IPasteur - Hervé Ménager		
FR-UNILorraine - Hrishikesh Dhondge		
CZ-MUNI - Helge Hecht		
CH-SIB - Alexander Kanitz		
DE-FZJU - Michael R. Crusoe		
DE-Freiburg - Sebastian Schaaf		
EMBL-HD - Renato Alves		
External		
AUS-Melbourne - Johan Gustafsson		
Objectives		
<p>To address the increasing complexity of life science analytics ELIXIR communities need access to advanced and large scale compute capacities, often in an international context. They need to be able to do so using sustainable compute resources which requires appropriate regulatory compliance, accounting and provenance. While aspects of this have and are being addressed by the e-infrastructures in Europe, life scientists have additional demands for computing sensitive data which only increases the importance of appropriate audit trails which will fit with the relevant information governance and security requirements.</p> <p>In this WP5, ELIXIR will identify best practices in our communities, Nodes and projects in the reporting of resources (facilities, services) used to lay the groundwork for billing or other financial accounting of services (within or between institutions, and eventually across borders). The Platform will identify automated, lightweight solutions which are FAIR in practice in order to track provenance. In turn this will improve the reproducibility of scientific analysis and the recognition of relevant service providers as well as researchers at the individual and organisational level. The Compute Platform is directly involved in relevant technical developments in secure and distributed computing in the Nodes and can help address the integration of non automated systems such as electronic notebooks.</p>		

Description of Work

Activity 1: Best practices, upscaling to build FAIR workflows using WorkflowHub in Communities

Leads: BE-VIB (Rafael Andrade Buono), Stian Soiland-Reyes (UK)

Our focus is to promote best practices for workflows, with a particular emphasis on WorkflowHub, leveraged by Communities. This will be facilitated via a white-paper to Communities in order to kickstart their contributions to WorkflowHub and build exemplar datasets. All our efforts will be wrapped up with best practices for workflows documentation (including EDAM ontology and crosslinks) and outreach. An important aspect is the seamless invocation of the workflows between WorkflowHub and Galaxy to upscale our users.

This will build on initial work by the Workflows Community Initiative's working group for FAIR Computational Workflows which are gathering best practices across workflow systems, as well as EuroScienceGateway's approach to workflow citation in scholarly communication.

APIs, like the GA4GH TRS endpoint, will be used for more WorkflowHub integration across the Tools Ecosystem.

Plan of work:

- Develop and communicate a set of training materials to contribute, and use WorkflowHub
- Enhance the UI and UX to publish, share and reuse workflows in Galaxy and WorkflowHub
- Community oriented workshops (1 day) or online
- Practices for curators to empower domain specific communities
- Plan and prototype a "workflow management plan"

Activity 2: Environmental impact of Galaxy and bioinformatics

leads: Nicola Soranzo (UK), Björn Grüning (DE)

We recognize that our operations have an impact on the environment, and we are committed to reducing this impact through a variety of targeted initiatives, using Galaxy, its associated ecosystem and its very wide number of users as a prime use case. We will also consider the relationships with RO-Crate and relevant schemas across ELIXIR to facilitate the work. Our first step will be to conduct a comprehensive assessment of our operations and to identify areas where we can reduce our environmental footprint. We will then communicate our findings and progress to the wider scientific community, fostering a culture of transparency and accountability around environmental impact. We will help raise awareness of the environmental impact of research and finally, we will develop and implement a range of mitigation strategies. Data collected by Galaxy and optimizations done will be integrated back into the Research Software Ecosystem, e.g. OpenEBench and coordinated with the Compute Platform (WP5). All our activities will be linked with the ELIXIR Focus Group for environmental impact.

Plan of work:

- Identify use cases (e.g. resource-hungry workflows) and ascertain their environmental footprint. Establish links with ELIXIR STEERS
- Accounting of energy consumption per workflow, visible to the user
- Coordinate with [HORIZON-INFRA-2023-tech-01-01](#) and [HORIZON-INFRA-2024-dev-01-03](#) projects for computing measures
- Galaxy will collect information relevant for the environmental impact assessment and provide them to the user (link to WP5 in the Compute Platform).

Activity 3: Flexible upscaling of FAIR workflows

leads: Rafael Andrade Buono (VIB, BE), Stian Soiland-Reyes (ELIXIR-UK)

Upscaling of workflows is important for handling large volumes of scientific data (e.g. using GPUs and HPC), but can act as a restriction on FAIR principles, limiting the number of computing infrastructures you can in practice run them on and thus reducing their reusability. However these requirements are not currently well described when defining the workflow and sharing it in repositories like WorkflowHub.

This task will take advantage of ongoing work for optimising upscaling of workflows, in particular EuroScienceGateway and the Pulsar network for federated compute, and reflect on changes needed for ELIXIR Cloud to fully support scalable workflows while retaining “just enough” FAIR aspects. Implementations will enable selective federated upscaled computation of workflows, taking into consideration transport time (workflow sent to compute nearest data) and environmental impact (WP5.2).

Plan of work:

- Alignment with the EOSC EuroScienceGateway project
- Utilisation of the European distributed compute network (Pulsar-Network) to democratise compute infrastructure
- Job scheduling will be done by taking data-locality and/or environmental impact into consideration

Deliverable	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
D5.1	Onboarding and training for registering workflows	BE-VIB	Mo4
D5.2	New metadata displayed by Galaxy workflow API and UI for energy consumption	DE-Freiburg	M18
D5.3	Developed and implemented a range of mitigation strategies for reducing the environmental impact	UK-Earlham	M36
Milestone	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
M5.1	Prototype a “workflow management plan”	UK-Earlham	M18
M5.2	Workshop and hackathon on environmental impact	DE-Freiburg	M11
M5.3	Enhanced WorkflowHub metadata to store computational requirements	BE-VIB	M24

Table of Deliverables and Milestones

Deliverable / Milestone	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
D5.1	Onboarding and training for registering workflows	BE-VIB	Mo4
D1.1	Annual Report 2023	FR-IPasteur	Mo6
M3.1	Selection of the particular community/domain for the best practices	ES-BSC	Mo6
M4.1	Selection of two communities from within the ELIXIR Priorities and Ambitions	IT-UNIBO	Mo6
M3.5	Improved mappings to the major linked open data resources, incl. the most relevant ontologies	NO-UiB	M11
M5.2	Workshop and hackathon on environmental impact	DE-Freiburg	M11
M1.1	Platform F2F Event - Year 1	ES-BSC	M12
D1.2	Annual Report 2024	DE-Freiburg	M18
D5.2	New metadata displayed by Galaxy workflow API and UI for energy consumption	DE-Freiburg	M18
M3.3	A list of the existing efforts that are capturing/describing research software quality	ES-BSC	M18
M5.1	Prototype a "workflow management plan"	UK-Earham	M18
M3.6	Refined, updated EDAM concepts supporting the needs of engaged ELIXIR Communities and Services	NO-UiB	M23
D2.3	Recommendations for software developers/authors, reviewers and editors for dissemination of research software metadata	NL-Leiden	M24
D4.3	First ARM-compatible Biocontainers deployed	FR-IRISA	M24
M1.2	Platform F2F Event - Year 2	DE-Freiburg	M24
M2.1	Review of software metadata edition systems and components that are available, for life sciences research and beyond	CZ-MUNI	M24
M2.2	Gap review of bio.tools UI	DK-DSU	M24
M5.3	Enhanced WorkflowHub metadata to store computational requirements	BE-VIB	M24
D2.5	Alignment and consolidation of Bioschemas (Tool, Workflow), biotoolsSchema, and CodeMeta	FR-CNRS	M26
D4.1	FAIRification of the benchmarking datasets from the communities selected in M3.1, including an investigation into the respective metadata schemas that can be employed (Bioschemas, etc)	IT-UNIBO	M26

Deliverable / Milestone	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
D1.3	Annual Report 2025	ES-BSC	M30
D1.4	Alignment to prospective ELIXIR Cross Platform dissemination articles	FR-IPasteur	M30
D1.5	Preparation, writing and delivery of 2027-2028 Platform Plan	ES-BSC	M30
D1.6	End Report	DE-Freiburg	M36
D2.1	Full design plans to implement or adapt an existing solution that provides the required functionalities. These plans would include a UI static prototype that specifies the features of the finished product	CZ-MUNI	M36
D2.2	Mockup and design plan to implement a new version of the bio.tools search user interface	DK-DSU	M36
D2.4	Outreach to external stakeholders and plan for continuous engagement	NL-Leiden	M36
D2.6	Prototype(s) to connect with prioritised ML registries relevant for the Research Software Ecosystem users	NO-UiB	M36
D3.1	A first version of the ELIXIR maSMP	ES-BSC	M36
D3.2	A mapping of the selected software quality indicators against the indicators produced or captured by OpenEBench, ELIXIR maSMP, Software Observatory and other services of the ELIXIR Research Software Ecosystem	ES-BSC	M36
D3.3	A new version of EDAM, incorporating updates for ELIXIR Communities, Services, and AI applications	NO-UiB	M36
D4.2	Facilitate connection of the benchmarking datasets within the OpenEBench ecosystem	IT-UNIBO	M36
D5.3	Developed and implemented a range of mitigation strategies for reducing the environmental impact	UK-Earlham	M36
M1.3	Platform F2F Event - Year 3	FR-IPasteur	M36
M3.2	A set of simple best practices, produced for the selected domain	ES-BSC	M36
M3.4	A learning pathway focused on software best practices	ES-BSC	M36

Appendix: Partner information

Institution	Contact Name
DE-Freiburg	Björn Grüning
ES-BSC	Salvador Capella
FR-IPasteur	Hervé Ménager
BE-VIB	Rafael Buono
CH-SIB	Ana Claudia Sima
CZ-MUNI	Adrián Rošinec
CZ-MUNI	Radka Svobodová
CZ-MUNI	Tomáš Raček
DE-FZJU	Michael R. Crusoe
DK-DSU	Veit Schwämmle
DK-UNICOP	Piotr Jaroslaw Chmura
EE-UTARTU	Hedi Peterson
ELIXIR-HUB	Jonathan Tedds
ELIXIR-HUB	Mihail Anton
EMBL-HD	Renato Alves
FR-CNRS	Alban Gaignard
FR-IRISA	Mateo Boudet
FR-UNILorraine	Hrishikesh Dhondge
GR-INAB/CERTH	Fotis Psomopoulos
IT-UNIBO	Emidio Capriotti
IT-UNIBO	Castrense Savojardo
IT-UNIBO	Pier Luigi Martelli
IT-UNIROMA1	Allegra Via

NL-Leiden	Magnus Palmblad
NO-UiB	Matúš Kalaš
SE-UU	Dimitris Bampalikis
UK-UNIMAN	Stian Soiland-Reyes
UK-Earlham	Nicola Soranzo
AU-Melbourne	Johan Gustafsson
DE-ZBMed	Leyla Castro
US-CALMI	Bhavesh Patel